

TWENTY-THIRD INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON COMPOSITE MATERIALS (ICCM23)

Probabilistic evaluation of filament-wound composite pressure vessel under material uncertainty

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August 02, 2023

Composite pressure vessels for fuel cell vehicles

Yoshida and Kojima, 2015

TOYOTA

HYUNDAI

HONDA

- ✓ Hydrogen fuel cell technology: clean and emissions-free
- ✓ Motors powered by electricity: hydrogen-powered vehicles complementing battery electric cars
- ✓ Hydrogen storage: safe, lightweight and cost-competitive
- ✓ Type IV pressure vessels: thin polymer liner overwrapped with carbon fibers wound layers

Probabilistic structural design

- ✓ Reliability analyses are vital to quantify and evaluate structural safety
- ✓ Stress-strength reliability approach
- ✓ Distributions compared: applied stress to strength

INPUT (X) – Distribution of primitive variables

- Lamina stiffness

E_1 [GPa]
 E_2 [GPa]
 G_{12} [GPa]
 ν_{12} [-]

MATERIAL

- Lamina strength

X_T [MPa]
 X_C [MPa]
 Y_T [MPa]
 Y_C [MPa]
 S [MPa]

MODELING

- Analytical
- CLT formulation

RESPONSE (Y) – Distribution of response

- Uncertainty propagation

- Sensitivity analysis

This work investigates:

- Effects of uncertainties on structural performance
- Filament-wound pressure vessels
- Burst pressure
- Type IV composite pressure vessels (COPV)
- Variability in material properties
- Probabilistic design: uncertainty and sensitivity analyses

Case study and general guidelines

- Based on the work from *Alam et. al* (2020)
- Type IV: CF/Epoxy
- Layup: $[-13^\circ/+13^\circ/+88^\circ/-13^\circ/+13^\circ]$
- $t_{\text{helical}} = 0,8382 \text{ mm}$; $t_{\text{hoop}} = 0,2286 \text{ mm}$

Alam et. al, 2020

Strength analysis

- Static, linear elastic
- Design: burst pressure
- First Ply Failure (FPF)
- Classical Laminate Theory
- Failure criterion: Max Stress

Probabilistic evaluation

- Monte Carlo Simulation with random sampling: 1,000 simulations
- Random input variables: material properties
- Normal distribution
- Uncertainty propagation: PDF + CDF
- Sensitivity analyses: Pearson's coefficients + One-factor-at-a-time investigation

T800/epoxy

Parameter	Mean	Std. deviation
E_1 [GPa]	176.8	8.0
E_2 [GPa]	10.336	0.519
ν_{12} [-]	0.3300	0.0208
G_{12} [GPa]	4.895	0.296
X^T [MPa]	3364.8	112.0
X^C [MPa]	1723.75	137.9
Y^T [MPa]	96.53	3.99
Y^C [MPa]	289.59	16.11
S [MPa]	96.53	0.59

Uncertainty Analysis

Histogram

Cumulative density function - CDF

- P_{burst} from Alam *et al.* (2020)
→ FEM: 15.64 MPa;
experiments - mean: 16.09 MPa
- Different hypotheses:
→ Non-linear geometry and material,
dome modeling

Pearson's correlation coefficients

Parameter	Correlation coefficient
E_2	-0.4909
γ^c	-0.0589
χ^c	-0.0540
S	-0.0447
χ^T	-0.0263
ν_{12}	+0.0290
G_{12}	+0.0291
E_1	+0.3883
γ^T	+0.7485

Sensitivity Analysis

Tornado plot: One-factor-at-a-time analysis

- γ^T, E_1, E_2 : stronger correlations
- γ^T : dominates the burst pressure
→ Its variation will reflect in a wider fluctuation of P_{burst}

- ✓ Probabilistic investigation of strength of COPV conducted
- ✓ Simplified analytical methodology able to describe the effect of uncertainties of material properties on structural performance
- ✓ Uncertainty propagation and sensibility analysis
- ✓ Allowable burst pressure of COPV more sensitive to Y_T (most), E_2 and E_1
- ✓ Design may vary with changes in vessel geometry (such as layup, thickness), failure criteria, among other
- ✓ Better understanding of limitations of current deterministic design strategies

Got book?

Thank you